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Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem and Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria

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In recent decades, environmental sustainability and economic growth have become intertwined priorities in both developed and emerging economies. As nations face growing challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, pollution, and unsustainable patterns of consumption, there is a strong global push to transition towards green and inclusive economic models. Within this context, the Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem (GEE) has emerged as a crucial enabler of sustainable economic growth. GEE refers to the interconnected set of institutions, networks, policies, and entrepreneurial actors working collaboratively to foster environmentally friendly innovations, eco-business models, and green start-ups (Cai et al., 2020). By supporting green entrepreneurship, such ecosystems facilitate the creation of new ventures that not only generate income and employment but also contribute to solving pressing environmental and social challenges (Acs et al., 2018).

Globally, green entrepreneurial ecosystems have demonstrated potential in advancing sustainable economic growth a model of development that ensures the simultaneous achievement of economic progress, environmental preservation, and social well-being (Kraus et al., 2020). Green-oriented entrepreneurs often develop innovative businesses in clean energy, waste-to-wealth initiatives, recycling, sustainable agriculture, and eco-friendly construction. This dynamic contributes to structural economic transformation, job creation, and resilience against environmental shocks (El-Kassar & Singh, 2019). Importantly, green entrepreneurial ecosystems foster cross-sectoral collaboration between businesses, government institutions, academia, and civil society, creating the enabling environment for long-term sustainable business practices (Bai et al., 2021).

In South East Nigeria, the need for a green entrepreneurial ecosystem is particularly critical. The region is marked by vibrant entrepreneurial activity but faces ecological challenges such as waste mismanagement, deforestation, poor energy infrastructure, and environmental degradation resulting from urbanization and industrialization (Okafor & Onuoha, 2021). Entrepreneurship has long been a driver of socioeconomic activity in the region; however,

ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives were to; examine the effect of green financing on Sustainable Economic Growth and evaluate the effect the sustainable Infrastructure development on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria. For the investigation, a descriptive survey design was chosen. Data for the study was gathered using a structured questionnaire design that included a five-point Likert scale. Descriptive statistics were utilized to examine and characterize the acquired data, and multiple regression analysis was employed to assess hypotheses. The result revealed that green financing has a significant positive effect on Sustainable Economic Growth with a p-value of (0.037<0.05). Sustainable Infrastructure development has a significant positive effect on Sustainable Economic Growth with a p-value of (0.000<0.05) in South East Nigeria. The study concluded that green entrepreneurial ecosystem significant positive effect on sustainable economic growth in South East Nigeria. The study recommended that financial institutions and government agencies should develop tailored financial products that support green entrepreneurs. This includes low-interest loans, grants, and investment funds focused on sustainable projects, making it easier for businesses to access capital for eco-friendly initiatives.

Keywords: Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem; Sustainable Economic Growth; South East Nigeria

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many businesses still focus on short-term profitability without embedding sustainability practices into their models. This misalignment hinders sustainable growth and limits the potential for green-driven innovation. Establishing and nurturing a GEE in South East Nigeria could help redirect entrepreneurial energy towards ventures that balance profitability with ecological and social goals, thereby transforming the region into a hub for inclusive growth.

Despite its evident importance, research indicates that Nigeria currently lacks a well-developed green entrepreneurial ecosystem due to weak institutional structures, inadequate financing, limited awareness, and insufficient policy support (Ndugbu & Okeke, 2022). South East Nigeria, in particular, while endowed with entrepreneurial dynamism, struggles with fragmented support systems for eco-innovation, limited government incentives, and minimal collaboration among stakeholders. As a result, the region is yet to fully harness the potential of green entrepreneurship as a mechanism for achieving sustainable economic growth, in line with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goals 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), and 13 (Climate Action) (United Nations, 2021).

Therefore, examining the effect of the green entrepreneurial ecosystem on sustainable economic growth in South East Nigeria is both timely and significant. Such an inquiry will provide empirical insights into how eco-entrepreneurship, institutional frameworks, and supportive networks contribute to sustainable development in the region. It will also generate recommendations for policymakers, academics, and practitioners to design and strengthen entrepreneurial ecosystems that align with global environmental and developmental priorities.

Statement of the Problem

The concept of a Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem (GEE) has gained increasing attention as a vital component for fostering sustainable economic growth, particularly in regions like South East Nigeria, where environmental challenges and economic development are intertwined. Despite the potential benefits of GEE, there is a notable gap in understanding how its components such as access to funding, supportive policies, educational resources, and networking opportunities affect sustainable economic growth in this region.

In South East Nigeria, characterized by rich natural resources and a burgeoning entrepreneurial spirit, the lack of a robust green entrepreneurial framework has hindered the transition to sustainable practices among local businesses. This has resulted in environmental degradation, resource depletion, and a failure to capitalize on the economic opportunities presented by green technologies and sustainable business models.

Furthermore, existing literature on the relationship between entrepreneurial ecosystems and economic growth often overlooks the specific dynamics of green entrepreneurship, particularly in developing regions. Consequently, there is an urgent need to investigate the effect of GEE on sustainable economic growth in South East Nigeria, identifying the barriers and enablers that influence the effectiveness of green ventures. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the interplay between green entrepreneurship and sustainable economic development, providing insights that can inform policy and practice to promote a more sustainable future for the region.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Examine the effect of green financing on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the effect the sustainable Infrastructure development on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria.

Hypotheses of the Study

- i. Green financing has no significant effect on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria.
- ii. Sustainable Infrastructure development has no significant effect on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

Isenberg (2011) describes the Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem (GEE) as a network made up of various interconnected actors, institutions, and processes that help entrepreneurs create environmentally friendly innovations and business models, thereby fostering sustainability transitions. Building on this, Muñoz and Cohen (2018) explain that the green entrepreneurial ecosystem promotes the development and growth of sustainable businesses through supportive institutional frameworks, green financing options, and cultural norms centered around sustainability. They highlight that GEEs are not solely focused on establishing green companies; they also aim to integrate sustainability values into the culture and governance of the ecosystem. According to Audretsch et al. (2023), the green entrepreneurial ecosystem embodies the merging of sustainability-oriented institutions, policies, and networks with entrepreneurial activities to establish conditions that encourage sustainable entrepreneurship. Nylund et al. (2021) characterize the GEE as a multi-layered system that connects entrepreneurial efforts with environmental responsibility by bringing together startups, investors, policymakers, and civil society around shared sustainability goals.

Liu and Stephens (2019) describe green entrepreneurial ecosystems as "dynamic networks" that provide not just traditional resources like finance, knowledge, and markets, but also weave ecological values and sustainability practices into entrepreneurial activities. They emphasize that these ecological values are vital resources that influence business models and innovation pathways. Audretsch, Belitski, and Caiazza (2022) illustrate how green entrepreneurial ecosystems drive regional competitiveness by promoting green innovation and sustainable business practices. These ecosystems align entrepreneurial incentives with environmental and social objectives, ensuring that regions remain resilient and competitive in the long run. Many scholars agree that GEEs encompass more than just clusters of entrepreneurs; they represent a systemic approach that integrates ecological values, supportive institutions, cultural norms, and financial mechanisms within entrepreneurial ecosystems. Given the increasing global challenges posed by climate change and resource scarcity, GEEs are becoming crucial frameworks for fostering sustainable regional development and ecological entrepreneurship (Bamini et al., 2025).

Green Financing

Green finance serves as an essential tool for balancing economic growth with environmental sustainability. Clapp and Helleiner (2025) define green finance as comprising "a multitude of public and private financial initiatives, instruments, and institutions aimed at developing environmentally focused financial services, funds, projects, policies, and commodities." These efforts are designed to support global goals for climate adaptation and mitigation, as well as biodiversity preservation. Green financing includes a variety of financial products and services that promote environmental sustainability, such as green bonds, green loans, and investments in renewable energy projects (Oneya and Jemaiyo, 2025). Sachs et al. (2019) further describe green financing as "financial systems and mechanisms that direct funds toward projects and companies contributing to low-carbon and climate-resilient growth." This perspective integrates climate finance into the broader green financing framework, highlighting its critical role in tackling global climate challenges and fulfilling international agreements.

Green finance plays a pivotal role in channeling funds toward sustainable trade and investment activities, providing low-risk financing, and developing green investment instruments (Snigdha et al., 2024). At the heart of this transformation is the concept of green financing, which includes a variety of financial products and services aimed at supporting environmentally sustainable projects and initiatives. This idea aligns with the broader framework of sustainable banking, which incorporates environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria into financial decision-making processes. This approach helps mitigate environmental risks, enhance reputations, and tap into new market opportunities (Valavan, 2024). Furthermore, Pathania and Kaushik (2024) emphasize that green financing is crucial for tackling global environmental issues while also promoting economic growth. It aids in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those focused on climate action (SDG 13), affordable and clean energy (SDG 7), and sustainable cities and communities (SDG 11). The rising regulatory pressures and increased awareness among stakeholders regarding environmental challenges have led banks to integrate green financing into their operations (Agrawal et al., 2024).

Sustainable Infrastructure Development

Sustainable Infrastructure Development takes a comprehensive approach to building infrastructure, ensuring that systems are planned, constructed, operated, maintained, and decommissioned in ways that protect the

environment, promote social equity, ensure economic viability, and foster long-term resilience (Kustova, Hudenko & Lace, 2024). According to guidance from the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB), sustainable infrastructure involves integrating technical, social, environmental, and financial analyses to inform decisions throughout the project lifecycle. This approach helps practitioners translate broad objectives into practical procurement, design, and monitoring practices (IDB, 2018). Sustainable Infrastructure Development emphasizes life-cycle thinking, considering not just the initial design and construction but also operational aspects (like energy and water use), adaptability to changes (such as climate change and demographic shifts), and end-of-life considerations (including decommissioning and recycling) (Kustova, Hudenko & Lace, 2024).

This approach contributes to broader societal goals, including the achievement of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), enhancing climate resilience, and minimizing negative environmental impacts. Sustainable infrastructure development involves mobilizing and directing various types of finance, whether public, private, blended, or multilateral, toward projects that aim to lower carbon footprints, enhance resilience, and promote social inclusion, all while ensuring these projects are financially viable and transparently governed. Various organizations and authors highlight different facets of this central concept. The United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals articulate the broader vision: infrastructure should be resilient and facilitate inclusive industrialization and innovation (SDG 9). This underscores the importance of durability, innovation, and accessibility, ensuring that infrastructure benefits all segments of society fairly (UNEP, 2021). To achieve sustainable infrastructure development, it is essential to foster technical innovation and align financing with governance reforms. Viewing this as an integrated policy and practice agenda rather than merely an engineering challenge is crucial for meeting the SDGs and climate targets (Munyasya & Chileshe, 2018).

Sustainable Economic Growth

Sustainable economic growth refers to economic activities that enhance the quality of life and overall welfare of society. It also signifies a level of economic growth that can be sustained over time without leading to significant future challenges. Essentially, sustainable economic growth is about increasing a nation's wealth and productive capacity in a way that doesn't compromise the ability of future generations to meet their needs. This concept integrates economic progress, environmental protection, and social inclusion (Pearce and Barbier, 2020). The primary aim of sustainable economic growth is to elevate the standard of living for both current and future generations. This is achieved by finding a balance between social advancement, environmental stewardship, and economic success (Todaro and Smith, 2020).

Sustainable growth means that the benefits of economic growth are shared widely, helping to reduce poverty, address inequality, and ensure that all segments of society can participate in and benefit from this growth. It is inherently multi-dimensional, linking economic indicators with measures of human development, equity, and environmental health. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and various national strategies put sustainable growth into practice by combining GDP growth with goals for poverty reduction, decent work, and environmental sustainability. This approach acknowledges that the legitimacy and sustainability of growth depend on who reaps the benefits and how well environmental risks are managed (Rusu & Oprean-Stan, 2025). When achieved, sustainable economic growth provides numerous long-term advantages, including resilience to economic shocks, health improvements, sustainable job creation and innovation, international legitimacy and investment, as well as well-being for future generations (Ul Haq, Huo & Saba, 2024).

Theoretical Reviews

Pecking Order Theory (POT)

The Pecking Order Theory (POT), introduced by Myers and Majluf in 1984, is a key framework in corporate finance that explains how firms choose their sources of financing. According to this theory, companies prefer to use internal funds, such as retained earnings, before turning to external financing. This preference arises from information asymmetry between managers and investors, which can create challenges in raising funds (Culata and Gunarsih, 2012). When external financing is necessary, firms tend to favor debt over equity because it incurs lower costs related to adverse selection. As the transition to sustainable and low-carbon economies demands significant investment, green projects often encounter higher risks and uncertainties compared to traditional investments. POT suggests that companies are likely to rely on internal funding to support green initiatives, especially if these projects are experimental or uncertain (Eburajolo, Ogiemudia, & Usifoh, 2023).

When applying the Pecking Order Theory (POT) to green finance, researchers point to the rising significance of green debt instruments, particularly green bonds, as a preferred option over equity issuance. Green bonds enable

companies to attract environmentally conscious investors while maintaining their ownership structures, thus minimizing the dilution often associated with issuing equity. Empirical studies indicate that firms are increasingly turning to green bonds to balance their cost of capital, enhance their reputation, and take advantage of regulatory incentives (Flammer, 2021). This trend aligns with POT's prediction that companies tend to favor debt financing when external funding is necessary.

Modernization Theory

Modernization Theory, originally articulated by Walt W. Rostow in 1960, views development as a progressive journey in which societies transition from "traditional" to "modern" economies through industrialization, the adoption of new technologies, and substantial investments in infrastructure. In its traditional interpretation, the theory emphasizes infrastructure such as transport, energy, water, and communications as both a driver and a defining feature of economic growth. Durable physical systems facilitate productivity improvements, market integration, and structural changes (Marks, 2009). However, scholars are now suggesting that we should rethink infrastructure investments. Instead of viewing them solely as projects aimed at expanding capital, they should be seen as systems designed for decarbonization and social inclusion (Meng, 2024).

Modernization Theory continues to be a valuable framework for understanding why nations prioritize infrastructure as a key strategy for development. However, its relevance today depends on adapting its principles to meet contemporary challenges. When modernization is combined with the principles of ecological modernization, life-cycle assessments, and governance reforms that promote green finance while safeguarding essential natural resources, it can pave the way for sustainable infrastructure. This approach helps reconcile the goals of productivity, resilience, and environmental stewardship (Sharma, 2024).

Empirical Reviews

Rangwaga & Dlamini (2021) conducted a study to investigate the intervention strategies for developing economies to create sustainable built infrastructure in several countries in Africa. The study aims to investigate possible ways in which developing economies can create sustainable built infrastructure while mitigating the concerns around excessive use of fossil fuels and non-recyclable materials. The study utilized the sectoral analysis. The results revealed that sustainable built infrastructure development is demanding a different approach that safeguards the environment and its finite resources within the context of an ethically, culturally, and socially valuable development process.

Mishra & Kannaujia (2023) conducted a study to review green finance instruments (green banking, green insurance, green bonds, etc.), their role in supporting sustainable development, opportunities, and challenges for adoption in India. The study aims to explore the various components of green finance that assist in achieving sustainability objectives, to assess the many green funding options available, and to evaluate the advantages and challenges of green finance. The study adopted a descriptive / literature review article (secondary-data synthesis). The results revealed that green finance supports sustainable energy management, improves corporate and institutional reputation, can attract FDI to green projects, and helps protect the environment by channeling funds to renewable energy, waste management, and biodiversity protection.

Awasthi et al. (2024) conducted a study to examine sustainable infrastructure design in urban settings and explores both the benefits and trade-offs or challenges of implementing sustainable infrastructure in urban cities of India. The study aims to assess how new ideas and technologies support sustainable infrastructure in urban contexts, to critically evaluate domains such as green infrastructure, smart city technologies (IoT, AI), renewable energy integration (solar, wind, hydropower, geothermal), circular economy, resilience, and social equality and to identify successful case studies of smart city projects and to analyze how these projects have enhanced urban infrastructure resilience and reduced greenhouse gas emissions. The study utilized a narrative review. The results revealed that sustainable infrastructure design holds potential to substantially address urban challenges but in order to realize the benefits, there must be supportive policy, regulatory frameworks, adequate financing, stakeholder engagement, technological readiness.

Oneya and Jemaiyo (2025) conducted a study to examine the interplay between green financing and the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya, with a particular focus on the role of corporate governance as a moderating variable. The study aims to evaluate the correlation between carbon asset financing and the financial outcomes of these banks, to explore the connection between environmental credit and the financial performance

metrics within the Kenyan banking sector, analyze the relationship between carbon emission allowances and the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya, to assess the role of corporate governance as a moderating factor in the relationship between green financing and the financial performance of commercial banks in the country. The study adopted a comprehensive review of scholarly articles, reports from the Kenya Bankers Association, and various working papers accessed via Google Scholar. The results revealed a favorable relationship between green financing initiatives and enhanced financial performance.

Methodology

A study design's primary objective is to establish a framework for gathering, analyzing, and interpreting data. This study will use a descriptive survey design to detail the data and characteristics of the target group. This approach seeks to collect real, precise, and organized data while offering insights into the subjects under study. It is particularly helpful given the size of the population from which the data is derived. The study was conducted in a few Southeast Nigerian private sectors that prioritize integrity. This study used a survey research approach to examine the impact of green innovation on the growth of new business prospects in Southeast Nigeria. Nigeria. Data was gathered using the right tools, including surveys with a five-point Likert scale.

The survey was crucial for gathering the key data needed to look at the relationships between variables. The collected data was coded and then imported into SPSS for analysis. To ensure accurate recording of relevant attributes, the data was coded and altered. Descriptive statistics were then utilized to analyze and characterize the data, and multiple regression analysis was employed to assess the hypotheses. If regression statistical measurements fell below the $\alpha = 0.05$ significance level, they were considered valid and significant.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data Presentation

The study involved 236 participants; 180 or so questionnaires were filled out and returned, resulting in a satisfactory return rate of 76.3%; the data was evaluated using descriptive and correlation analysis; The tables below display the results of a pilot test of 36 questionnaires, which yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.775, suggesting satisfactory reliability.

Results

Gender of Respondents

The research population was more female than male, as the pie chart below shows.

Table 1: Gender Distribution of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	107	59.4	59.4	59.4
	Female	73	40.6	40.6	100.0
	Total	180	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Age Distribution of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Under 21 years	8	4.4	4.4	4.4
	21-30 years	109	60.6	60.6	65.0
	31-40 years	49	27.2	27.2	92.2
	Above 40 years	14	7.8	7.8	100.0
	Total	180	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents' Location

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Urban	117	65.0	65.4	65.4
	Local	62	34.4	34.6	100.0
	Total	179	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.6		
Total		180	100.0		

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents' Educational Level

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below High School	6	3.3	3.3	3.3
	High School Graduate	31	17.2	17.2	20.6
	University Degree	131	72.8	72.8	93.3
	Master's or Higher	12	6.7	6.7	100.0
	Total	180	100.0	100.0	

Tables 1-4 displays the demographic data of the respondents, including gender, age, location, and educational background. Approximately 107 responses, or 59% of the total, are men, according to the data. The largest age group, comprising over 109 respondents (61%), is between 21 and 30 years old. Geographically, the majority of participants 117 individuals, or 65% of the sample come from metropolitan areas. Lastly, 131 respondents (72.8%) held a university degree, which is a noteworthy ratio when it comes to educational background.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 5: Multiple Regression Table

Model 1	Beta	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-value
Green Financing (GT)	0.71145	0.41319	1.72184	0.031
Sustainable Infrastructure Development (SID)	0.22714	0.03241	7.00833	0.000
Constant	2.90181	0.11028	26.3131	0.000
Adj R ²	0.698			

Source: SPSS version 28.0

Table 5 above displays the results of the multiple regression analysis for hypotheses one and two. Every predictor variable significantly affects the result variables, according to this study, which was conducted at a 5% significance level. More details are provided in the following hypothesis.

Hypotheses of the study

Hypothesis One

- i. **H₀₁: Green financing has no significant effect on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria.**

Regression Model of Hypothesis 1

Below is the equation for a model for Hypothesis 1

$$SEG = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GF + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

SEG= Sustainable Economic Growth

GF = Green Financing

Table 6: Regression Coefficient for model 1

Model 1	Beta	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-value
Green Financing (GF)	0.71199	0.41319	1.72315	0.037
Constant	2.90181	0.11028	26.3131	0.000
Adj R ²	0.698			

Source: SPSS version 28.0

Table 6 shows the adjusted R Square, unstandardized beta coefficient, standard error, t value, and P value. With a corrected R square value of 0.698, Green Financing (GF) are responsible for 69.8% of the variation in Sustainable Economic Growth (SEG); factors not included in this model are responsible for the remaining variation in SEG. Furthermore, the unstandardized beta coefficient is 0.71199, which indicates that the Sustainable Economic Growth (SEG) will climb by 0.71199 units for every unit increase in Green Financing (GF). This effect is statistically significant with a p-value of =0.037 and a 95% CI of less than 0.05. Therefore, it can be said that the null hypothesis is rejected and that Green Financing (GF) significantly impact the Sustainable Economic Growth (SEG) in southeast Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

- ii. **H₀₁: Sustainable Infrastructure development has no significant effect on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria.**

Regression Model of Hypothesis 2

Below is the equation for a model for Hypotheses 2

$$SEG = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SID + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

SEG= Sustainable Economic Growth

SID = Sustainable Infrastructure Development

Table 7: Regression Coefficient for Model 2

Model 1	Beta	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-value
Sustainable Infrastructure Development (SID)	0.22714	0.03241	7.00833	0.000
Constant	2.90181	0.11028	26.3131	0.000
Adj R ²	0.698			

Source: SPSS version 28.0

Table 7 shows the adjusted R Square, unstandardized beta coefficient, standard error, t value, and P value. Sustainable Infrastructure Development (SID) explain 69.8% of the variation in Sustainable Economic Growth (SEG), according to the adjusted R square value of 0.698. Factors not included in this model are responsible for the remaining variation in SEG. Additionally, the unstandardized beta coefficient is 0.22714, which indicates that Sustainable Economic Growth (SEG) will increase by 0.22714 units for every unit increase in Sustainable Infrastructure Development (SID). This effect is statistically significant since the p-value is less than 0.000, or less than 0.05 at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and it can be inferred that Southeast Nigeria's Sustainable Economic Growth (SEG) is significantly affect by Sustainable Infrastructure Development (SID).

Discussion of Findings

The study examined the effect of Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem on Sustainable Economic Growth in South East Nigeria. The Cronbach's alpha for these specific items was 0.775, as shown in Table 4.1, suggesting that they were reliable for measuring the variables we selected. At a 5% level of significance for hypothesis one, the multiple linear regression results in Tables 4.4.1 and 4.4.2 show that green financing have a statistically significant effect on the sustainable economic growth prospects in Southeast Nigeria. On the other hand, hypothesis two states that the sustainable economic growth is statistically significantly impacted by sustainable infrastructure development at the 5% level of significance. This conclusion is based on their individual p-values, which are below the limit of < 0.05.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the establishment of a green entrepreneurial ecosystem is vital for promoting sustainable economic growth in Southeast Nigeria. The significant positive effects of green financing and sustainable infrastructure development underscore the importance of integrating environmental considerations into economic strategies. Green financing enhances access to capital for eco-friendly initiatives, enabling startups and established businesses to invest in sustainable practices that drive innovation and job creation.

Moreover, the development of sustainable infrastructure facilitates the efficient operation of green enterprises, providing the necessary support for their growth and scalability. This infrastructure not only addresses immediate

economic needs but also ensures long-term environmental sustainability, creating a resilient economy that can withstand future challenges. As Southeast Nigeria continues to embrace a green entrepreneurial ecosystem, it can unlock substantial opportunities for economic diversification and resilience. By fostering an environment conducive to green innovation and sustainable practices, the region can achieve balanced growth that benefits both the economy and the environment, paving the way for a sustainable future. The study concluded that green entrepreneurial ecosystem significant positive effect on sustainable economic growth in South East Nigeria.

Recommendations

Given the evidence that green financing and sustainable infrastructure development have significant positive effects on sustainable economic growth in South East Nigeria, it is recommended that deliberate efforts be made to strengthen the green entrepreneurial ecosystem within the region., the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. Financial institutions and government agencies should develop tailored financial products that support green entrepreneurs. This includes low-interest loans, grants, and investment funds focused on sustainable projects, making it easier for businesses to access capital for eco-friendly initiatives.
- ii. Foster collaborations between the public and private sectors to develop sustainable infrastructure. Such partnerships can leverage resources and expertise, resulting in the construction of green facilities, renewable energy projects, and efficient transportation systems that support economic growth.

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